

UNVEILING THE SYNERGISTIC EFFECTS OF SiC AND GRAPHITE REINFORCEMENTS ON THE MICROSTRUCTURE, MECHANICAL PROPERTIES, AND WEAR PERFORMANCE OF STIR-CAST AL-7079 COMPOSITES.

Vijayanand

Research Scholar , Research Center of Industrial and Production Engineering, Poojya Doddappa Appa College of Engineering, Kalaburagi, E-mail:-profvijay1010@gmail.com

Dr.M.S.Uppin

Professor & HOD, Industrial and Production Engineering, Poojya Doddappa Appa College of Engineering, Kalaburagi, India E-mail:-msuppin@yahoo.com

Abstract

The stircasting process was employed to fabricate composites using Al-7079 alloy as the matrix material, reinforced with SiC and graphite. Microstructural analysis, mechanical property evaluation, and wear testing were conducted on the composites. The microstructure of the as-cast Al-7079 alloy comprised various phases formed during solidification, including the primary alpha (α) phase and the eutectic phase. The Al/3Gr composite exhibited a heterogeneous and non-uniform distribution of graphite particles, forming agglomerations. Micrographs of the hybrid composites showed the presence of SiC and graphite particles within the aluminium matrix. Increasing the wt.% of SiC and Gr to 10 and 5, respectively, significantly increased the area fraction of reinforcement. However, the graphite reinforcement resulted in higher agglomerations and poor interface formation with the matrix. The ultimate tensile strength (UTS) varied among the composites. The as-cast Al-7079 demonstrated a UTS of 206 MPa with a % elongation of 14.5%. The addition of 3 wt.% SiC as reinforcement improved the UTS to 222 MPa, a 7.7% increase compared to the initial as-cast strength. However, replacing the reinforcement with graphite at the same weight percentage reduced the UTS to 198.8 MPa, a decrease of 3.9%. Microhardness measurements showed a similar trend, with SiC addition enhancing hardness compared to the as-cast alloy, while graphite inclusion resulted in a slight decrease. The hybrid composites Al/5SiC/3Gr and Al/10SiC/5Gr exhibited microhardness values of 70 HV and 73 HV, respectively, surpassing those of the as-cast Al-7079. Wear testing revealed that the as-cast Al-7079 experienced the highest weight loss and wear rate. The addition of 3 wt.% SiC improved wear properties, while 3 wt.% graphite resulted in a similar wear rate to the SiC-reinforced composite. Surprisingly, the hybrid composites Al/5SiC/3Gr and Al/10SiC/5Gr exhibited the lowest wear rates. Mild wear in the graphitic composites was primarily influenced by the formation of tribo-layers on contact surfaces, while severe wear resulted in the removal of tribo-layers and a significant reduction in surface hardness.

Keywords: Stir casting, Al-7079 alloy, SiC, graphite, microstructure, mechanical properties, wear properties.

1. Introduction

Metal matrix composites (MMCs) have gained significant attention in recent years due to their unique properties that make them suitable for a wide range of applications across industries,

including the automobile and aerospace sectors [1–3]. The specific characteristics of particulate-reinforced aluminum matrix composites have made them highly suitable for the automotive and aerospace industries. Their unique characteristics encompass low density, high specific strength and stiffness, favorable fatigue properties, dimensional stability at elevated temperatures, and satisfactory tribological properties [4–8]. As a result, these composites have found wide-ranging applications. The aluminum matrix composites that incorporate both SiC and Gr particles as reinforcements have shown enhanced tribological performance when compared to composites reinforced with either SiC or Gr alone [9]. Wear and friction coefficient are commonly used indicators to assess the tribological response of composites [6]. The majority of research articles focus on the wear of composites, while only a few touches upon the friction coefficient, which serves as an indicator of energy loss in any tribosystem [10–12]. The results concerning the friction coefficient provide evidence of its dependence and independence on the fraction of reinforcements in the composites [6, 13, 14]. Hybrid aluminum metal matrix composites reinforced with silicon carbide (SiC) and graphite (Gr) are extensively used due to their high strength and wear resistance [15].

Akhlaghi et al. [16] mentioned in their research work that the Al/Gr/SiC hybrid composites are attracting attention due to their high wear resistance and low friction coefficient. The graphite acts as a solid lubricant but weakens the composite's mechanical properties. SiC particles compensate for this by increasing hardness and strength. Traditional powder metallurgy (P/M) requires a long mixing time, but a new method called "in situ powder metallurgy (IPM)" was used to prepare Al/SiC/Gr hybrids in this study. The effects of SiC content on morphology, density, microstructure, hardness, and wear properties were examined. The study conducted by Mahdavi et al. [9] introduces a new method called in situ powder metallurgy (IPM) for preparing Al6061/SiC/Gr hybrid composites. It combines stir casting and powder metallurgy into an integrated net shape forming process. SiC particles (0- 40 vol.%) and uncoated Gr particles (9 vol.%) are added to molten 6061 aluminum alloy, resulting in mixtures of SiC, Gr, and aluminum powder particles. The powder mixtures are cold pressed and sintered, followed by heat treatment. The composites exhibit homogenous distribution of SiC and Gr particles, improved hardness, and decreased compressibility. The hybrid composite with 20 vol.% SiC particles achieves the best wear resistance. Dhoria SH et al. [17] fabricated hybrid 6351-Al/Gr/SiC composites through squeeze casting, utilizing 6351 aluminium alloy as the matrix and graphite and silicon carbide particles as reinforcements. The study focuses on evaluating the mechanical properties, including hardness and tensile strength, through Vicker's hardness and tensile tests. Additionally, wear tests were conducted to examine the wear rate. Results show that hardness and tensile strength increase with higher SiC content and lower Gr content. Furthermore, the wear rate of all composites increases with higher applied load.

Suresha et al. [18] processed hybrid 6351 Al/Gr/SiC composites using squeeze casting method. Mechanical properties (hardness, tensile strength) were evaluated via tests, and wear rate was studied. Results indicate increasing hardness and tensile strength with higher SiC content and lower Gr content, while wear rate increases with higher applied load. Another work by the same authors [19] concluded that the use of graphite (Gr) reinforcement in aluminum matrix composites reduces wear but weakens mechanical strength. Silicon carbide (SiC) improves both strength and wear resistance but makes machining difficult and the composites brittle. To address this, SiC can be used as a secondary reinforcement in hybrid composites. The hybrid

composites exhibited improved hardness and wear behavior, but wear increased beyond 7.5% reinforcement of SiC and Gr. Riahi et al. [20] found that the coefficient of friction of A356-10% SiC-4% Gr composite is lower than that of A356-20% SiC composite under constant load and speed conditions, and that the former value declines and the latter grows beyond 80 N and up to 150 N at sliding speed of 2.0 m/s. Similar friction behavior can be found in aluminum matrix composites with reinforcements other than SiC/Gr. According to Wu et al. [21] the ratio of aluminosilicate to Al-12Si alloy reinforcement gradually increased by 3-7% after the coefficient of friction decreased by up to 4.5%.

Therefore, it is clear from these research that the results are widely scattered, which may be the better outcome for one of the parameters on compromising other. There may be justifications for the scatter in parametric investigations. In this article, a set of experiments is used to investigate the effects of combined reinforcement (SiC and Gr particles), on the microstructural, mechanical and wear behavior of Al-SiC-Gr hybrid composites.

2. Experimental procedure

2.1. Fabrication of composite

The Al-70079 alloy was used as a matrix material. Table 1 represents the elemental composition as analysed by the ED-XRF spectrometer. The SiC (silicon carbide) and graphite particles are used as reinforcement. The average particle size of the SiC and graphite particles were measured to be $\leq 50 \mu\text{m}$.

Table. 1 Elemental composition of the Al-7079 analyzed by ED-XRF.

Elements	Cu	Fe	Mg	Mn	Si	Ti	Zn	Al
Nominal composition	0.3-1	≤ 0.6	1.2-2.0	0.30-0.80	≤ 0.40	≤ 0.20	7.0-8.0	Remaining
Composition measure by ED-XRF	0.35	0.52	1.52	0.61	0.2	0.09	7.5	89.21

The stir casting setup is depicted in Fig. 1b. A 1000-gram sample of aluminium was collected in a SiC crucible, placed in an electric resistance furnace, and heated to 700 °C. As the aluminium melted, Ca₂Cl₆ was added to degas the entrapped air. A zirconia-coated mechanical stirrer was dipped into the melt and rotated at 300 rpm. The reinforcement powder was transferred to the melt at a constant feed rate, ensuring homogeneous distribution and no agglomeration. Five castings with different weight fractions of the reinforcements were fabricated, and the details of the reinforcements added to the base Al-7079 is reported in Table 2. During casting, the stirring was continued for 5 minutes, maintaining the furnace temperature at 700 °C. Then the melt was poured into the cast iron mould of 150 mm length and 18 mm diameter. The castings were allowed to cool to room temperature and used as the initial composite specimens.

Figure 1. Electrical Resistance Furnace (Stir casting set up), Addition of degassing Tablet hexa-chloro ethane.

2.2. Characterization of composite

2.2.1 Microstructure

To study the microstructure of the fabricated composites, the cast material is cut into small sections (1 cm by 1 cm) and mounted using a mounting machine. The samples are then polished using emery sheets with grit sizes of 220 to 2000. The final mirror polishing is done by using disc polishing machine. The polished samples are then etched using Keller's reagent. Then the samples are observed under the SEM (scanning electron microscope).

2.2.2. Mechanical properties.

In order to understand the tensile behaviour of the fabricated composites, the cylindrical shaped specimens were prepared according to ASTM-E8 standards. The tensile test was conducted using a 100 KN Hydraulic automated screw driven Universal testing machine at AML, Bangalore. The test results were collected, and the mean value of three ultimate tensile test values was considered.

Similarly, the micro-hardness was determined using the Vickers microhardness test. The test was conducted according to ASTM E-384 using a Mitutoyo HM-200 machine with a 100gm load and a 10-second dwell time. The average of the seven indentations was used to measure each sample's hardness value.

2.2.3. Wear properties

The wear test is conducted on pin-on-disc machine in order to understand the wear behaviour of the fabricated composites (refer Fig. 2). Test specimens were cut into pin shape of dimensions 30 mm in length and 8 mm diameter. The pin specimens are then mounted into the holder of pin-on-disc wear testing machine, attaching the pin holder to the load cell. The test parameters are adjusted, such as rotational speed, normal load, and sliding distance.

The test results were collected, including the weight loss, changes in dimensions, and surface characteristics of the sample. Then the wear rate was calculated by dividing the weight loss by the sliding distance or time period. The wear track and surface of the sample was observed under the SEM microscopy for better understanding of the wear mechanisms. Finally, the data were analysed and the relevant charts, graphs, and images are reported.

Figure 2. Pin-on-disc wear testing machine used to conduct wear test.

Table: 2 The reinforcement compositions of the fabricated composites and their abbreviations used in present paper.

Sl.No	Composite composition	Abbreviation
1	As cast Al-7079	Al-7079
2	Al-7079/3 wt. % SiC	Al/3SiC
3	Al-7079/3 wt. % Gr	Al/3Gr
4	Al-7079/5 wt. % SiC & 3 wt. % Gr	Al/5SiC/3Gr
5	Al-7079/10 wt. % SiC & 5 wt. % Gr	Al/10SiC/5Gr

3. Results and Discussion

The ED-XRF analysis of the matrix material which conforms the elemental composition of the matrix material, which is depicted in Fig.3. The table shows the nominal composition of the Al-7079 and the experimentally measured composition.

Figure 3. ED-XRF analysis of the Al-7079 matrix material for the confirmation of elemental composition.

3.1 Microstructure

The microstructure of the as-cast Al-7079 and the composites are depicted in Fig. 4 and Fig. 5. The microstructure of the as-cast Al-7079 alloy typically consists of various phases that form during solidification. The specific microstructure can vary depending on the casting process, cooling rate, and other factors. In general, the microstructure of Al-7079 comprises of primary Alpha (α) Phase and Eutectic phase (Fig. 4). The primary α phase in the microstructure of Al-7079 is the aluminum-rich matrix. This phase provides the alloy with its inherent strength and is composed mostly of aluminum atoms. Alongside, the eutectic phase is also present in the microstructure that forms when the alloy solidifies and consists of a combination of aluminum, zinc, and other alloying elements. It typically appears as inter-dendritic regions or small particles distributed within the matrix. Depending on the specific composition and processing conditions, secondary phases may also be present in the microstructure of Al-7079 alloy. Common secondary phases include precipitates of magnesium, copper, and other elements. These precipitates can contribute to the strengthening of the alloy and affect its mechanical properties.

Figure 4. The microstructure of as-cast Al-7079 alloy.

Figure 5 shows the SEM micrographs of the composites with various wt. % of SiC and Gr. Along with the matrix α -Al and eutectic phase the microstructure comprises of the reinforced SiC particles which are mainly trapped at the grain boundaries. The graphite particles in Al/3Gr composite on the other side has heterogeneity and non-uniform distribution. The agglomerations of the graphite particles can be clearly seen from the Fig. 5(b). The prime reason behind the graphite agglomeration is the poor wettability between the aluminum melt and the reinforcement graphite, that hinders the uniform distribution during solidification.

Figure 5(c & d) are the micrographs of hybrid composites, as we can see the SiC as well as the graphite particles in the matrix aluminum. As a result of further increment in the wt.% of the SiC and Gr to 10 and 5, the area fraction of the reinforcement increased drastically in the Fig. The seamless grain boundaries are composed of both SiC and the graphite. Notably, the graphite reinforcement has affected the composite structure to turn with higher agglomerations and poor interface formation with the matrix.

Figure 5. The SEM micrographs of different composites, a) Al/3SiC, b) Al/3Gr, c) Al/5SiC/3Gr and d) Al/10SiC/5Gr.

3.2 Tensile test

The variation in the ultimate tensile strength values are shown in Fig. 6. It can be seen that the UTS of the as cast Al-7079 is determined to be 206 MPa, which has a percentage elongation of 14.5%. The composites, on the other hand, showed remarkable variation in the UTS as well as the % elongation with the addition of SiC and graphite. The 3 wt.% SiC reinforced composite showed an UTS of 222 MPa, which is 7.7% better than the initial as- cast Al-7076 strength. On the other hand, by replacing the reinforcement to graphite with a similar weight percentage, the composite showed a diminishment in its strength properties. The UTS value of the composite

is observed to be 198.8 MPa, i.e., 3.9% of reduction. The increase in strength for the SiC reinforced composite is may be due to the dispersion strengthening, as the SiC particles are uniformly distributed throughout the composite, they act as a barrier to impede the dislocation movement, thereby improving the overall strength of the composite. Also, the load is transferred to SiC particles, which certainly have a higher modulus of elasticity compared to the matrix. This load transfer mechanism helps to distribute the stress more evenly throughout the composite, which reduces localized deformation and improves the overall strength. On the other hand, the graphite is a soft material with very less shear modulus, and when they added to the aluminum matrix, it acts as a stress concentrator and weakens the material. Also, the uniform distribution and homogeneous mixing of graphite in the aluminum melt is very difficult as there exist huge discrepancy in the densities of the both. Also, the wettability is poor between the graphite and aluminium melt. Hence, the strength of the Al-7079/3Gr composite is on the lower side.

Figure 6. The variation in the ultimate tensile strength of the Al-7079 and composites.

The hybrid composites of Al/5SiC/3Gr is fabricated to understand the properties of composites with the combination of both reinforcements. Surprisingly, the composite started showing improvement in strength even with the addition of graphite.\

The Al/5SiC/3Gr showed the ultimate tensile strength of 212.8 MPa, which is better than Al-3Gr but not near the strength of Al-SiC. Hence, reinforcement is needed if SiC is increased to 10% to see the effect. Expectedly, the mechanical properties further improved to 232.5 MPa, which is nearly 11% better than the as-cast Al-7079. As we can note, the addition of SiC has eventually improved the strength, but at the expense of the ductility, the reduction in the percentage elongation is a shred of evidence. Amongst all the specimens, the as-cast Al-7079 has a better percentage of elongation, and it has substantially decreased with the addition of reinforcement. The lowest percentage elongation was recorded for the Al/10SiC/5Gr, which is 10.2%.

Figure 7. The variation in the % elongation of the Al-7079 and composites.

3.3 Micro-hardness

As similar to the tensile strength, the microhardness also improved with the addition of SiC, and slightly on the lower side when the graphite is added. The microhardness of the as-cast Al-7079 is measured to be 65 HV. However, the reinforcement of 3 wt. % SiC improved the hardness to 72 HV. The microhardness of the hybrid composites Al/5SiC/3Gr and Al/10SiC/5Gr were 70 HV and 73HV, respectively, that are better than the as cast Al- 7079 (refer Fig. 8).

Figure 8. The microhardness of the Al-7079 and composites.

3.4 Wear Behavior

All the samples, along with the as-cast Al-7079, were subjected to a wear test as depicted in Fig. 9. The highest weight loss and wear rate were recorded for the as-cast Al-7079, and the wear properties seemed to be improved with the addition of 3 wt.% of SiC. Further, the addition of 3 wt.% graphite has shown nearly the same wear rate as the SiC added composite. Surprisingly, the hybrid composites Al/5SiC/3Gr and Al/10SiC/5Gr showed the lowest wear rates. It directly means that the addition of reinforcement SiC and graphite individually to 3 wt.% has certainly improved the wear properties of the Al-7079. The effect was greater when both SiC and Gr were added at once to make a hybrid composite. In order to analyse the effect, the worn samples are observed under the scanning electron microscope.

Figure 9. The wear rate of the Al-7079 and composites.

The SEM micrographs of the worn surfaces are shown in Fig. 10. The plastic deformation of the matrix seemed to be very commonly observed on the surface of as-cast Al-7079 and the composites with 3 wt.% of SiC and Gr. In Fig. (c), the longitudinal wear tracks were noticed, and that may be due to the deep penetration of the SiC particles. On the other hand, the graphite particles simply glide on the surface without causing the matrix to deform. The graphite has a unique layered structure, as described in the article. This makes graphite a well-known solid lubricant, and the reinforcement of such a solid lubricant in the matrix material makes the material a self-lubricating material. During the wear test, as the matrix material deforms and starts to wear, the reinforcement comes in to rescue the composite by reducing the interfacial friction coefficient. The reduced interfacial friction coefficient certainly reduces wear loss. This can be clearly seen in Fig. (d), where the graphite particles are sticking and sliding on the wear track (notice that the graphite sliding direction is the same as the wear track direction).

Figure 10. SEM micrograph of the worn surfaces of (a & b) as-cast Al-7079, c) Al/3SiC, d) Al/3Gr, e) Al/5SiC/3Gr, and f) Al/10SiC/5Gr.

In the graphitic composites, the transition to severe wear was accompanied by a significant decrease in the hardness of the worn surfaces (compared to those reached in mild wear, where

the tribo-layers were present; Fig. Consequently, during sliding wear, at the critical temperature, tribo-layers can leave the contact surface by sliding over the softened bulk material. Once the tribo-layer is removed from the contact surface, the bulk material becomes in direct contact with the counterface. Once the existing tribo-layer is stripped off, it is difficult to form a new tribo-layer on the hot and softened matrix. On the other hand, while comparing the mild-to-severe wear transition Mechanically mixed layers containing fractured hard particles were found on the surfaces of other (non-graphitic) aluminium matrix composites rubbed. The graphitic composites are clearly superior to the others in delaying the transition to severe wear and, hence, providing the best seizure resistance against the steel. It can be concluded that graphitic composites are well suited to applications where seizure resistance is important, such as cylinder liners in internal combustion engines. Mild wear in the graphitic composites was primarily controlled by the formation of the tribo-layers, or mechanically mixed and oxidised surface layers, on the contact surfaces. In the severe wear regime, the tribo-layers were removed, and the hardness of the worn surfaces was greatly reduced.

Conclusions

The conclusions drawn from the current research work are as follows:

- The microstructure of as-cast Al-7079 and its composites consists of a primary Alpha (α) Phase as the aluminum-rich matrix, along with eutectic phases and secondary precipitates, influencing the mechanical properties.
- The microstructure of the composites showed SiC particles predominantly at grain boundaries and graphite particles exhibiting heterogeneity and agglomerations.
- The addition of SiC and graphite increased the area fraction of reinforcement, but the graphite's poor wettability led to higher agglomerations and limited interface formation with the matrix.
- The addition of 3 wt.% SiC reinforcement in Al-7079 composites led to a significant increase in ultimate tensile strength (UTS) to 222 MPa, representing a 7.7% improvement over the initial as-cast.
- The hybrid composite Al/5SiC/3Gr exhibited an ultimate tensile strength of 212.8 MPa, surpassing the strength of Al-3Gr but not reaching the level of Al-SiC composites, prompting further investigation by increasing the SiC reinforcement to 10%, resulting in a remarkable improvement in mechanical properties 11% higher than that of the as-cast Al-7079.
- The addition of SiC enhanced strength, rather it led to a reduction in ductility, as evidenced by the significant decrease in % elongation across all specimens, with Al/10SiC/5Gr displaying the lowest % elongation at 10.2%.
- The addition of 3 wt.% SiC to as-cast Al-7079 resulted in a significant improvement in wear properties. Similarly, the inclusion of 3 wt.% graphite showed a comparable wear rate to the SiC-reinforced composite. Notably, the hybrid composites Al/5SiC/3Gr and Al/10SiC/5Gr exhibited the lowest wear rates, suggesting that the individual additions of SiC and graphite at 3 wt.% improved the wear properties of Al-7079.
- The presence of SiC particles in the composites led to plastic deformation of the matrix, resulting in longitudinal wear tracks, while the graphite particles exhibited a unique

layered structure and acted as a solid lubricant, reducing interfacial friction and wear loss, as observed in the wear test.

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